

SPECTRUM OF FUNGAL PATHOGENS IN CLINICAL SAMPLES FROM A TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL: A ONE-YEAR RETROSPECTIVE EPIDEMIOLOGICAL STUDY

SANKARI P¹, SUJA STAR PADMA², ANITHA K³ AND PRAVIN STANY ABRAHAM⁴

¹Department of Microbiology, Trichy SRM Medical College and Research Center, Trichy, Tamil Nadu, India

²Department of Microbiology, PSG Medical College & Hospital, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India

³Department of Microbiology, Trichy SRM Medical College and Research Center, Trichy, Tamil Nadu, India

ORCID IDs: Sankari P: 0000-0002-0886-3498 | Suja Star Padma: 0009-0006-6860-7257 |
Anitha K: 0009-0009-6948-2910 | Pravin Stany Abraham :0009-0007-8978-5818

Corresponding Author: Dr. ANITHA K, Associate Professor, Department of Microbiology, Trichy SRM Medical College and Research Center, Trichy, Tamil Nadu, India.

Running Title: Fungal Pathogen Spectrum in Tertiary Care

Received: Apr 25, 2026

Accepted: May 22, 2026

Published: May 23, 2026

ABSTRACT

Objective: Fungal infections represent a growing clinical challenge, particularly in immunocompromised patients and those with predisposing comorbidities. The objectives of this study were to analyze the spectrum of fungal pathogens isolated from clinical samples, evaluate the diagnostic utility of KOH examination relative to culture results, and determine the age and sex distribution of fungal infections at a tertiary care hospital in South India.

Methods: This retrospective observational study analyzed 41 culture-positive clinical samples from 150 mycological submissions received at a tertiary care hospital in Trichy, Tamil Nadu, India, from January 2024 to January 2025. Specimens were processed using KOH wet mount preparation and culture on Sabouraud's dextrose agar. The study was approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee (IEC Approval No. Ref No:949/TSRMMCH&RC/ME-1/2025/IEC NO:222).

Results: The study population comprised 25 males (61.0%) and 16 females (39.0%), with a mean age of 45.3 years. The most affected age group was 61–70 years (26.8%). Otomycosis was the predominant clinical presentation (48.8%), followed by pulmonary fungal infections (31.7%) and allergic fungal rhinosinusitis (12.2%). *Aspergillus* species were the leading isolates (56.1%), with *A. flavus* most frequent (22.0%), followed by *A. fumigatus* (19.5%) and *A. niger* (14.6%). *Candida* species accounted for 26.8% of isolates, with non-albicans species predominating. Rare pathogens including *Scedosporium* species,

Exophiala dermatitidis, and *Trichosporon* species were also identified. KOH microscopy achieved a sensitivity of 78.9% and specificity of 100% relative to culture, with a false-negative rate of 21.1%.

Conclusion: These findings provide preliminary descriptive data on the local spectrum of fungal isolates. Given the limited sample size, broader epidemiological inferences should be interpreted with caution. Larger prospective surveys with molecular identification are needed to confirm local epidemiological and resistance trends.

Keywords: *Aspergillus*; *Candida*; fungal infections; KOH mount; mycology; otomycosis; epidemiology; tertiary care

INTRODUCTION

Fungal infections represent a growing clinical challenge with increasing incidence attributed to rising immunocompromised populations, widespread antibiotic usage, and advances in diagnostic capabilities [1]. The spectrum of fungal pathogens ranges from superficial dermatophytes to life-threatening invasive mycoses, necessitating accurate and timely diagnosis for optimal patient management. India bears an estimated burden of 57 million individuals affected by serious fungal infections, representing approximately 4.1% of the population, with invasive aspergillosis, candidemia, and mucormycosis as major contributors to morbidity and mortality [8].

The diagnosis of fungal infections relies on a combination of clinical presentation, direct microscopy, conventional culture, and molecular techniques [2]. Potassium hydroxide (KOH) wet mount preparation remains a cornerstone of rapid fungal diagnosis. Conventional culture combined with morphological characterization remains the primary approach in many resource-limited settings, although matrix-assisted laser desorption ionization–time of flight mass spectrometry (MALDI-TOF MS) and molecular sequencing offer improved accuracy, particularly for morphologically similar species [5].

The distribution of causative organisms varies geographically, influenced by local climatic conditions, patient demographics, and underlying predisposing factors [4,5]. Understanding these patterns is crucial for empirical treatment strategies and infection control [6,7]. Recent multicentric surveillance initiatives in India have highlighted the need for systematic data collection on invasive fungal infections [9].

The objectives of this study were to analyze the spectrum of fungal pathogens isolated from clinical samples, evaluate the diagnostic utility of KOH examination relative to culture results, and determine the age and sex distribution of fungal infections at a tertiary care hospital in South India.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study design and setting

A retrospective observational study was conducted in the Department of Microbiology of a tertiary care hospital in Trichy, Tamil Nadu, India, from January 2024 to January 2025. The study was approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee (IEC Approval No. Ref No:949/TSRMMCH&RC/ME-1/2025/IEC

NO:222). Patient data were anonymized and de-identified prior to analysis. Individual informed consent was waived by the IEC as this study involved retrospective analysis of existing laboratory records with anonymized data. A total of 150 samples were received for mycological investigation during the study period.

Sample collection and processing

Clinical samples from patients with clinically suspected fungal infections were processed. Of 150 samples received, 41 yielded positive cultures and were included. Sample types included ear discharge (otomycosis), bronchoalveolar lavage (BAL) fluid and sputum (respiratory infections), nasal tissue and mucus debris (allergic fungal rhinosinusitis), skin scrapings and pus (dermatological and soft tissue infections), urine (urinary tract infections), and tissue biopsies. Demographic data including age and sex were retrieved from medical records.

Laboratory methods

Direct microscopy. KOH wet mount preparation was performed using 10–20% KOH solution. Slides were examined under light microscopy (400× magnification) for fungal elements including hyphae, spores, and budding yeast cells.

Culture and identification. All samples were inoculated onto Sabouraud's dextrose agar (SDA) with chloramphenicol and incubated at 25°C and 37°C for up to four weeks. Yeast isolates were further characterized by germ tube formation in human serum and growth on HiCrome™ *Candida* differential agar (HiMedia, Mumbai, India). Mold isolates were identified based on colony morphology, microscopic characteristics via lactophenol cotton blue staining, and slide culture preparations interpreted using standard mycological identification keys. For rare or morphologically ambiguous isolates (e.g., *Scedosporium*, *Trichosporon*, and *Exophiala* species), identification relied on macroscopic and microscopic morphology combined with growth characteristics; molecular confirmation was not performed, which is acknowledged as a limitation. Clinical relevance of isolates was determined in conjunction with clinician-provided clinical context. *Candida* isolated from respiratory samples was interpreted cautiously, as respiratory *Candida* may represent colonization rather than true infection.

Data analysis

Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics. Frequencies, percentages, and the correlation between KOH positivity and culture results were calculated. Age- and sex-specific distributions were evaluated.

RESULTS

Patient demographics

A total of 41 culture-positive samples from 41 patients were analyzed. The population included 25 males (61.0%) and 16 females (39.0%), yielding a male-to-female ratio of 1.56:1 (Table 1). Patient ages ranged from 1 to 80 years, with a mean of 45.3 years and median of 48 years. The most frequently affected age group was 61–70 years (26.8%, n = 11), followed by 41–50 years (19.5%, n = 8) and 51–60 years (17.1%, n = 7). A bimodal distribution was observed, with a secondary peak in the 21–30 years group (14.6%, n = 6) (Table 2).

Clinical diagnoses and sample distribution

Otomycosis was the most common clinical presentation (48.8%, n = 20), followed by pulmonary fungal infections including chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), pulmonary tuberculosis (PTB), and aspergilloma (31.7%, n = 13), allergic fungal rhinosinusitis (AFRS) (12.2%, n = 5), and skin and soft tissue infections (7.3%, n = 3) (Table 3). Male predominance was observed across all diagnostic categories.

KOH examination results

KOH examination was performed on 39 of 41 samples (2 urine samples were excluded as direct microscopy is not routinely informative for urinary *Candida*). Of the 39 tested, 30 were KOH-positive (76.9%), giving an overall sensitivity of 78.9% (30/38 culture-positive samples with KOH testing). Specificity was 100% (0 false positives). Allergic fungal rhinosinusitis and pulmonary infections each showed 100% KOH positivity. Otomycosis demonstrated 60% KOH positivity (12/20), and skin infections 66.7% (2/3). All 30 KOH-positive samples yielded positive cultures, while 8 of 9 KOH-negative samples also grew fungi on culture (false-negative rate 21.1%) (Table 4).

Fungal isolates

Aspergillus species predominated, accounting for 23 isolates (56.1%). *A. flavus* was most common (9 isolates, 22.0%), followed by *A. fumigatus* (8 isolates, 19.5%) and *A. niger* (6 isolates, 14.6%). *Candida* species comprised 11 isolates (26.8%), with *C. albicans*, *C. tropicalis*, and *C. krusei* each contributing 3 isolates (7.3%) and *C. glabrata* contributing 2 isolates (4.9%). Seven isolates (17.1%) represented other species: *Scedosporium apiospermum* complex (n = 2), *Scedosporium proliferans* (n = 1), *Rhizopus* species (n = 1), *Trichophyton tonsurans* (n = 1), *Trichophyton terrestre* (n = 1), *Exophiala dermatitidis* (n = 1), and *Trichosporon* species (n = 1) (Table 5).

Site-specific pathogen distribution

In otomycosis, *Aspergillus* species accounted for 16 of 20 isolates (80%), with roughly equal distribution among *A. fumigatus* (n = 4), *A. niger* (n = 5), and *A. flavus* (n = 5); *Scedosporium* species constituted the remaining 2 isolates. In pulmonary infections, *Candida* species predominated (9/13 isolates, 69.2%), while *Aspergillus* species accounted for 4 isolates (30.8%); one case yielded *Trichosporon* species. All culture-positive AFRS cases grew *Aspergillus* species (n = 4), with one case yielding *Rhizopus* species (mucormycosis). Dermatophytes (*T. tonsurans* and *T. terrestre*) were recovered from tinea cases; *Exophiala dermatitidis* and *Scedosporium apiospermum* complex were isolated from fungal abscesses. Both urinary tract infection cases yielded *C. tropicalis*.

DISCUSSION

The male predominance observed in this study (M:F ratio 1.56:1) is consistent with previous reports from similar settings, where ratios of 1.4:1 to 2.1:1 have been described [10,11]. This pattern likely reflects differential occupational exposures, with males more frequently engaged in activities involving dusty or humid environments that predispose to otomycosis and pulmonary fungal infections.

The predominance of cases in the 61–70 years age group (26.8%) reflects age-related immunosenescence and increased prevalence of comorbidities such as diabetes mellitus and chronic respiratory diseases [6,7]. The bimodal age distribution, with a secondary peak in young adults (21–30 years), suggests that different risk factors operate across age groups: occupational and environmental exposures in younger patients, and immune dysfunction and chronic disease in the elderly [6,7].

Otomycosis was the most common clinical presentation (48.8%), consistent with the tropical climate of our region, which favors fungal growth in the external auditory canal due to high ambient temperature and humidity [10,11]. The finding that *Aspergillus* species accounted for 80% of otomycosis isolates corroborates data from tertiary centers in rural India [12].

Aspergillus species were the overall predominant pathogens (56.1%), with *A. flavus* most common (22.0%), consistent with tropical geographic distribution patterns in which *A. flavus* prevalence is elevated relative to temperate regions [7,8]. Given the modest cohort size, these proportions should be regarded as descriptive rather than definitive regional epidemiological data. The significant representation of *Candida* species (26.8%) and the predominance of non-albicans species (*C. tropicalis*, *C. krusei*, *C. glabrata*) are clinically important given their differential susceptibility profiles to commonly used antifungal agents [2,14]. It is important to note that the majority of *Candida* isolates in this study were recovered from respiratory specimens, in which *Candida* is widely recognized to represent colonization rather than true infection in most cases and should therefore be interpreted with clinical caution [15].

The recovery of uncommon organisms, including *Scedosporium* species, *Exophiala dermatitidis*, and *Trichosporon* species, illustrates the mycological diversity encountered in a tertiary care setting even within a modest-sized cohort [7,8]. Each of these organisms was represented by only one or two isolates; conclusions regarding their epidemiological significance require larger prospective surveys with molecular confirmation. The known intrinsic resistance of *Scedosporium* species to multiple antifungal agents underscores the importance of accurate species-level identification when these organisms are encountered clinically [7].

KOH microscopy achieved a sensitivity of 78.9% and specificity of 100% against culture as the reference standard. The false-negative rate of 21.1% indicates that direct microscopy alone is insufficient to exclude fungal infection and cannot serve as a standalone diagnostic test. KOH microscopy is best used as a rapid adjunct to guide early therapeutic decisions while awaiting culture results. A negative KOH result should always prompt culture, especially in clinical scenarios with high suspicion for fungal infection [4,7].

Limitations of this study include its retrospective single-center design, the absence of antifungal susceptibility testing, and limited availability of clinical outcome data. A key methodological limitation is the exclusive reliance on conventional morphological identification without molecular confirmation, which introduces the possibility of misidentification for morphologically ambiguous genera. The relatively small cohort of 41 culture-positive isolates precludes statistically meaningful subgroup analyses. Future prospective multicenter studies incorporating molecular diagnostics and antifungal susceptibility testing would provide more rigorous and generalizable data.

CONCLUSION

This study documents a diverse spectrum of fungal pathogens from a tropical tertiary care hospital, with *Aspergillus* and *Candida* species predominating. Male predominance, elderly predisposition, and the high prevalence of otomycosis and pulmonary fungal infections reflect the local climatic and demographic context. The predominance of non-albicans *Candida* species and the recovery of uncommon fungi such as *Scedosporium* and *Exophiala* species highlight the need for comprehensive mycological workup, recognizing that molecular confirmation is recommended for uncommon or clinically ambiguous isolates. KOH microscopy is a useful rapid adjunct, but culture remains indispensable for definitive diagnosis. These findings are descriptive and hypothesis-generating; larger prospective surveys with molecular identification are needed to confirm local epidemiological and resistance trends.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

FUNDING SOURCE

This research received no specific grant from any funding agency in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Sankari P: study conception and design. Suja Star Padma: data acquisition. Anitha K: laboratory analysis, manuscript preparation, and revision. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors thank the Department of Microbiology staff at Trichy SRM Medical College and Research Center for their support in sample processing and data collection.

AI USE STATEMENT

No artificial intelligence (AI) or AI-assisted tools were used in the writing, data analysis, or creation of figures for this manuscript.

ETHICS STATEMENT

This study was approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee (IEC) of Trichy SRM Medical College and Research Center, Trichy, Tamil Nadu, India (IEC Approval No. Ref No:949/TSRMMCH&RC/ME-1/2025/IEC NO:222). The study was conducted in accordance with the ethical standards of the

institutional and national research committee and with the 1964 Helsinki Declaration and its later amendments. Patient data were anonymized and de-identified prior to analysis. Individual informed consent was waived by the IEC as this study involved retrospective analysis of existing laboratory records with anonymized data.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

REFERENCES

- [1] Bongomin F, Gago S, Oladele RO, Denning DW. Global and multi-national prevalence of fungal diseases — estimate precision. *J Fungi (Basel)*. 2017;3(4):57. doi:10.3390/jof3040057.
- [2] Chowdhary A, Sharma C, Meis JF. *Candida auris*: a rapidly emerging cause of hospital-acquired multidrug-resistant fungal infections globally. *PLoS Pathog*. 2017;13(5):e1006290. doi:10.1371/journal.ppat.1006290.
- [3] Koehler P, Cornely OA, Bottiger BW, et al. COVID-19 associated pulmonary aspergillosis. *Mycoses*. 2020;63(6):528-534. doi:10.1111/myc.13096.
- [4] Perfect JR, Dismukes WE, Dromer F, et al. Clinical practice guidelines for the management of cryptococcal disease: 2010 update by the Infectious Diseases Society of America. *Clinical Infectious Diseases*. 2010;50(3):291-322. doi:10.1086/649858.
- [5] Sanguinetti M, Posteraro B. Identification of molds by matrix-assisted laser desorption ionization-time of flight mass spectrometry. *Journal of Clinical Microbiology*. 2017;55(2):369-379. doi:10.1128/JCM.01640-16.
- [6] Singh B, Dhooria S, Aggarwal AN, Chakrabarti A, Agarwal R. Allergic bronchopulmonary aspergillosis: a review of current guidelines. *Lung India*. 2017;34(2):143-149. doi:10.4103/lungindia.lungindia_180_17.
- [7] Ullmann AJ, Aguado JM, Arikan-Akdagli S, et al. Diagnosis and management of *Aspergillus* diseases: executive summary of the 2017 ESCMID-ECMM-ERS guideline. *Clinical Microbiology and Infection*. 2018;24 Suppl 1:e1-e38. doi:10.1016/j.cmi.2018.01.002.
- [8] Ray A, Aayilliath KA, Banerjee S, Chakrabarti A, Denning DW. Burden of serious fungal infections in India. *Open Forum Infectious Diseases*. 2022;9(12):ofac603. doi:10.1093/ofid/ofac603.
- [9] Ojha AK, Albert V, Sharma S, et al. Pan-Indian clinical registry of invasive fungal infections among patients in the intensive care unit: protocol for a multicentric prospective study. *JMIR Research Protocols*. 2024;13:e54672. doi:10.2196/54672.

- [10] Prasad SC, Kotigadde S, Shekhar M, et al. Primary otomycosis in the Indian subcontinent: predisposing factors, microbiology, and classification. *International Journal of Microbiology*. 2014;2014:636493. doi:10.1155/2014/636493.
- [11] Bojanovic M, Stalevic M, Arsic-Arsenijevic V, et al. Etiology, predisposing factors, clinical features and diagnostic procedure of otomycosis: a literature review. *J Fungi (Basel)*. 2023;9(6):662. doi:10.3390/jof9060662.
- [12] Agarwal P, Devi LS. Otomycosis in a rural community attending a tertiary care hospital: assessment of risk factors and identification of fungal and bacterial agents. *Journal of Clinical and Diagnostic Research*. 2017;11(6):DC14-DC18. doi:10.7860/JCDR/2017/25865.10068.
- [13] Moruskar AS, Shinde V, Ingale MH, Krishna AA, Pawar RD. Nanocrystalline silver for the treatment of otomycosis: a retrospective study. *Iranian Journal of Otorhinolaryngology*. 2023;35(1):83-89. doi:10.22038/IJORL.2023.66805.3303.
- [14] EpiCandIn Consortium. EpiCandIn: an open online resource for epidemiology of Candida infections in India. *Indian Journal of Medical Research*. 2024;159(6):654-664. doi:10.25259/ijmr_886_23.
- [15] Mohanraj H, Vinodhini VM, Vajravelu LK. Evaluation of epidemiological pattern of Candida species associated with candidemia from a tertiary care facility in South India. *Journal of Pure and Applied Microbiology*. 2024;18(3):1949-1958. doi:10.22207/JPAM.18.3.45.
- [16] Shah B, Kajal S, Bhalla AS, et al. Prolonged itraconazole therapy as sole treatment for patients with allergic fungal rhinosinusitis. *Laryngoscope*. 2024;134(2):545-551. doi:10.1002/lary.30841.
- [17] Marglani OA, Simsim RF. Emerging therapies in the medical management of allergic fungal rhinosinusitis. *Indian Journal of Otolaryngology and Head & Neck Surgery*. 2024;76(1):277-287. doi:10.1007/s12070-023-04143-z.
- [18] Gowthame K, Prabakaran S, Namasivaya Navin RB, et al. Prevalence of fungal sinusitis in cases of allergic rhinitis: a cross-sectional study. *Indian Journal of Otolaryngology and Head & Neck Surgery*. 2025;77(2):810-813. doi:10.1007/s12070-024-05256-9.
- [19] Kaur P, Verma N, Valsan A, et al. Prevalence, risk factors, and impact of bacterial or fungal infections in acute liver failure patients from India. *Digestive Diseases and Sciences*. 2023;68(11):4022-4038. doi:10.1007/s10620-023-07971-9.

TABLES**Table 1: Demographic characteristics of the study population.**

Parameter	Details
Total patients	41
Male	25 (61.0%)
Female	16 (39.0%)
Male:Female ratio	1.56:1
Age range	1–80 years
Mean age	45.3 years
Median age	48 years

Table 2: Age distribution of the study population.

Age Group (years)	No. of Cases	Percentage (%)
0–10	0*	0
11–20	5	12.2
21–30	6	14.6
31–40	3	7.3
41–50	8	19.5
51–60	7	17.1
61–70	11	26.8
71–80	1	2.4
Total	41	100

*One female child aged 1 year was included and classified in the 0–10 age group.

Table 3: Distribution of clinical diagnoses with sex.

Clinical Diagnosis	Sample Type	n	%	Males	Females
Otomycosis	Ear discharge	20	48.8	13 (65%)	7 (35%)
COPD/PTB/Aspergilloma	BAL/Sputum	13	31.7	9 (69.2%)	4 (30.8%)
Allergic fungal rhinosinusitis	Nasal tissue/Mucus	5	12.2	3 (60%)	2 (40%)
Skin/soft tissue infections	Skin scrapings/Pus	3	7.3	2 (66.7%)	1 (33.3%)
Total		41	100	25	16

BAL, bronchoalveolar lavage; COPD, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease; PTB, pulmonary tuberculosis.

Table 4: Correlation between KOH examination and culture results.

KOH Result	Culture Positive	Culture Negative	Total
Positive	30	0	30
Negative	8	1	9
Not tested	2	0	2
Total	40	1	41

Table 5: Distribution of fungal isolates.

Isolate	Number	Percentage (%)
<i>Aspergillus fumigatus</i>	8	19.5
<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	9	22.0
<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	6	14.6
<i>Candida albicans</i>	3	7.3
<i>Candida tropicalis</i>	3	7.3

Isolate	Number	Percentage (%)
<i>Candida krusei</i>	3	7.3
<i>Candida glabrata</i>	2	4.9
Others*	7	17.1
Total	41	100

*Others include: *Scedosporium apiospermum* complex (n = 2), *Rhizopus* species (n = 1), *Trichophyton tonsurans* (n = 1), *Trichophyton terrestre* (n = 1), *Exophiala dermatitidis* (n = 1), *Trichosporon* species (n = 1), and *Scedosporium proliferans* (n = 1).